

Pan-Islam and the Caliphate 1880-1930

By: Louloua Awad

The struggle over Pan-Islamism in the late 19th and early 20th centuries was not merely a contest of political ideologies but a psychological and geopolitical battle that would shape the future of the Muslim world. Count Léon Ostrorog, "The British Empire and the Mohammedans" (1918) and Shakib Arslan, "Islam and Nationalism" in *Our Decline: Its Causes and Remedies* (1930) represent two opposing visions of Islam's place in modernity, with one serving as an imperial blueprint for domination and the other as a call for resistance and self-determination. Ostrorog, a French legal scholar and Ottoman advisor, wrote for European policymakers and colonial administrators, to persuade them of the necessity of reforming Islamic governance under Western oversight, portraying Islam as in need of external guidance. He advances the myth of benevolent rule, projecting imperial anxieties and contradictions onto Muslim societies they sought to dominate, while justifying the erasure of indigenous governance structures that did not align with Western liberal values. Meanwhile Arslan, a Druze intellectual and prominent Pan-Islamist, directly refutes this vision, arguing that colonial manipulation, particularly the suppression of Muslim confidence and the imposition of economic and political stagnation, created a self-fulfilling prophecy of inferiority. His work, aimed at a Muslim readership, seeks to reignite a sense of agency, unity and self-sufficiency in the face of European domination to restore Muslim sovereignty by reminding them of their capabilities, past achievements, and the true essence of their religion. Together, the two texts illustrate both ends of the spectrum of colonial manipulation, demonstrating how liberal paternalism justified intervention while psychological subjugation ensured compliance. By exposing the use of strategic paternalism, ideological coercion, and the forced dichotomy of modernization versus westernization, the authors dissect the mechanism behind the decline of Pan-Islamism and the eventual deterioration of the Caliphate, showing how imperial narratives reshaped both Muslim governance and self-perception.

Ostrorog begins by revealing Pan-Islamism and the Caliphate as threats to British and French colonial dominance, framing their intervention as essential to maintain control. He reinforces Britain's fear of losing power over Muslim populations, warning that failing to dictate the fate of the Caliphate after Britain's defeat at the Dardanelles left it "...impossible either to...admit that it should be settled according to German views, since such an acquiescence...would have... the definite ruin of our moral ascendancy over Mohammedan Asia and Africa" (Ostrorog, 2). The phrase "moral ascendancy" exposes Britain's psychological strategy of ensuring Muslims internalized British rule as preferable to self-governance. Britain not only sought to suppress pan-islamic unity but actively manipulated Islamic leadership for geopolitical gain, using Islam as a weapon against Germany, the Ottomans, and anti-colonial movements. This strategy played out in the Sykes-Picot agreement (1916) that created artificial borders to divide Muslim-majority lands, ensuring no unified Islamic power could rise to challenge British and French rule. Ostrorog makes Britain's intention explicit when he states, "The British crown holds in its hands a trump card of marvellous efficiency for ensuring a satisfactory solution of the Mohammedan problem" (Ostrorog, 10). The term "trump card" reveals this is a tactical maneuver, not a genuine concern for muslim well-being, while "Mohammedan problem" stresses how muslim political unity was perceived as a direct threat and destabilizing force that needed to be neutralized.

Beyond political fragmentation, Ostrorog's strategy aimed to reshape Islam itself to fit within a colonial framework. He argues that for Islam to be saved it must be reformed in a way to reconcile it with British ideals, stating, "If islam is to be saved to civilization, reconciled with progress, ... the Gate of Interpretation must be opened once again" (Ostrorog, 18). By invoking ijthihad while simultaneously discrediting Islam, Ostrorog appropriates an internalistic Islamic debate to position Britain as the arbiter of religious reform to destabilize Islamic unity. He disregards Mohhamed abduh's legitimate modernization efforts, which were co-opted by the British to weaken traditional scholars and justify intervention. Ostrorog then emphasizes that this must be done "with the help -very cautious and diplomatic- of Christian rulers of Islam, and especially the British Crown" (Ostrorog, 24), stripping Islam of political autonomy and framing it as something to be governed rather than respected. His language

reflects blatant paternalism, reinforcing Britain's self-appointed role as Islam's caretaker. His assertion that intervention would dispel "...forever the nightmare of hundreds of millions of Mohammedens living in the darkness and fanaticism of medieval ignorance..." (Ostrorog, 25) reflects classic Orientalist assumptions that Islam had stagnated since the Middle Ages, while speaking on behalf of Muslims and their so-called 'nightmare'. By concluding with Britain's intervention serving the "furtherance of human liberty and enlightenment" (Ostrorog, 28), he mirrors the rhetoric of the "White Man's Burden," masking imperial control as benevolent guidance and moral duty rather than a power scheme. Overall, Ostrorog's work reflects the power of narrative control in shaping future political discourse, with pan-islam as a prime example.

On the other hand, Arslan exposes the enduring repercussions of these Western-imposed hierarchies, illustrating how psychological manipulation and physical suppression instilled a deep-seated lack of Muslim self confidence. He begins by describing the depth and complexity behind this process: "When the Europeans knew of this condition, which serves their colonial interests, they went on reporting it and reinforcing it, until Muslims reached a stage described in the Qur'an: 'In their hearts is a disease: And Allah has increased their disease'" (Arslan, 98). Europeans ensured that Muslims internalized these ideas, leading to a self-fulfilling prophecy of stagnation. He emphasizes that colonial powers deliberately promoted this mindset to maintain control, explaining that such propaganda is "facilitating for them to colonize Muslim lands...saves them from competition on resources, gives them undisputed supremacy, and unquestioned control" (Arslan, 98). By confronting the realities behind the manipulation, Arslan aims to reach his Muslim audience and dismantle this manufactured inferiority complex, reassuring them that "There is no difference in human potentiality" (Arslan, 99). He argues that the real obstacle was not Islam itself but the colonial structures that fostered economic dependency and suppressed Muslim self-reliance.

To illustrate the deliberate suppression of Pan-Islam, Arslan points out how European powers actively sabotaged Muslim-led infrastructure projects to maintain their dominance. The Hijaz Railway, connecting Damascus to Medina, was a major Ottoman project designed to facilitate pilgrimage and trade. This was initially mocked by even Westernized Muslims as Arslan mentions "truly, many Muslims did

not believe it” (Arslan, 102), yet the railway’s success reducing travel time to two days, proved that Muslim-led modernization was possible. This reality was quickly undermined by the British and French after WWI by halting the railway, an economic and symbolic attack on Muslim unity: “...the first thing the English and French colonialists did was to halt this railway, which linked Sham to Arabia, bringing Muslims close to each other” (Arslan, 103). This was not just about land control but about severing economic and political connections among Muslim regions. More dangerously, colonial influence eroded internal Muslim attitudes and confidence, fostering the belief and eventual reality that “...we do not find any worthwhile economic entity in the Muslim world which is not run either by the Europeans or the Jews... It is as though the only thing Muslims can do in this world is to be labourers, unable to employ their minds” (Arslan, 104). This demonstrates how foreign control systematically weakened Muslim agency and economic independence. The true result of colonial intervention was not progress, but the deliberate suppression of Muslim self-sufficiency and a deep-rooted psychological dependency on foreign powers.

European imperial narratives often depicted Islamic civilization as inherently stagnant and resistant to modernization without Western intervention. Ostrorog explicitly reinforces this stereotype, claiming that “the Arab brain, once so active and fruitful, stopped working, and, ever since, the Mohammedan conception of things has remained dry, barren and incapable of movement as an Egyptian mummy in its narrow prison of bands” (Ostrorog, 16). His diction and comparison to a mummy relays imagery of decay, presenting Islam as a relic of the past, frozen in time, unable to adapt to modernity. He develops this Western understanding of Islam by claiming, “Science and reasoning are represented as opposed to one another” (Ostrorog, 18), presenting it as anti-intellectual and an impediment to scientific progress. This framing extends to enable interference in Islamic governance and religious institutions as he portrays Muslim scholars as reactionary forces actively preventing reform, stating that “ The ulemas organised such an upheaval against him that if he had not been rescued by a number of liberal minded young officers, he would have been torn to pieces by the infuriated mob” (Ostrorog, 24). By depicting the ulema as violent, intolerant, and stubborn, Ostrorog implies that Islam itself is the root of Muslim decline.

This narrative of irrational fanaticism legitimized European efforts to dismantle traditional institutions and replace them with Western-compatible “reformist” figures, such as Sir Syed Ahmad Khan, who promoted a version of Islam aligned with British colonial rule.

Arslan presents Ostrorog’s narrative as fabrication and selective amnesia, arguing that Muslim historical achievements and economic self-sufficiency were disrupted by colonial interference rather than inherent shortcomings. He refutes claims of Muslim incapability, asking “If Muslims are not good at all in these sciences, as you claim, how, then, did they manage to create all the wonderful civilizational monuments which up to now are attractions for tourists from all over the world?” (Arslan, 99). To remind people of Muslim success, he lists thriving institutions and industries across Egypt, Syria, Iraq, India, Iran, and North Africa, and cites figures like Talaat Basha Harb, who proved the possibility of economic revival and independence: “It was as though he was carving rocks...their faith remained in the foreign banks until they saw...the near miraculous success of the Bank of Egypt” (Arslan, 106). The bank’s capital rapidly expanded to over 20 million pounds at 18 years, financing textile factories, shipping, and film production, all of which were once monopolized by Europeans, proving that when given autonomy, Muslim societies could thrive. The same growth occurred through a Palestinian bank, reinforcing that local enterprises could succeed without European backing. Arslan also challenges the belief that secularism is a prerequisite for progress. He points out the West’s own reliance on religious foundation “Does anyone in the East believe that the awakening in the West was achieved without any religious training? ‘Our culture is based on Christianity,’” (Arslan, 95). To demonstrate that true Islamic rule, can do the same, he cites the transformation of Hijaz under King ‘Abd al-Aziz ibn Sa’ud whose strict application of shari’ah law brought stability and economic growth which “wouldn't have become a reality without the strong will and determination, coupled with faith in Allah and self-confidence” (Arslan, 112). This was even acknowledged by Western observers as one noted, “he wished that his country, America, were as peaceful as what he saw in Yemen and Hijaz (Arslan, 111). The Western perception of Muslims as chaotic, aggressive, and backward was not a reflection of their nature but a consequence of constant suppression. When allowed self-determination, they established harmony through infrastructure projects

involving diverting floodwaters, improved pilgrimage routes, expanded agriculture, and proposed Zamzam water exports (Arslan, 116), directly disproving colonial myths of Muslim incompetence.

Ostrorog's colonial strategy relied on political fragmentation; driving a wedge between Arabs and the Ottoman Turks to weaken Muslim unity and make British intervention appear both necessary and desirable. He presents the Ottoman Caliphate as an illegitimate oppressive force preventing Arab self-determination, arguing that "The Turkish Han is a spurious caliph, and cannot be anything but a spurious caliph" (Ostrorog, 7). By discrediting the Ottoman leadership, he shifts blame for Arab struggles away from European colonialism and onto their own rulers. This tactic mirrors broader British strategies, such as the Hashemite-Saudi rivalry, where Britain allied with Abdulaziz Ibn Saud in 1915 to challenge Hashemite rule and ensure continued Arab disunity. He further fuels Arab resentment against the Ottomans by depicting them as tyrannical suppressors of free thought, labeling discussions on the Quraysh requirement for the Caliphate as the "state secret" (Ostrorog, 9) and claiming they banned the Saheeh al-Bukhari hadith despite lacking strong historical proof. Ironically, Britain was doing this themselves in Egypt, as their authorities maintained control over Al-Azhar university, selectively allowing scholars who complied with colonial rule while suppressing those issuing anti-colonial fatwas. Ostrorog's further comparison of Turkish rule to Prussian rule over the Poles again, projects European intentions while attempting to create a new enemy for the Arabs. This aligns with Britain's orchestration of the Arab Revolt (1916-1918), where an engineered anti-Ottoman uprising was framed as an organic nationalist movement. Ostrorog's insistence that the Caliphate be transferred to an Arab ruler, one with "precautions as would ensure its entire and docile sympathy with the Allies" (Ostrorog, 13), reveals this was not about genuine Arab sovereignty but about manipulatively securing a puppet leadership that would comply with British interests, as attempted before. His rhetoric attempts to convince Arabs that their liberation lies in Western-mediated reforms, rather than in Muslim self-determination, making them unwitting participants in their own subjugation.

British propaganda played a key role in fragmenting and controlling the Muslim world by instilling a sense of inferiority, prompting Arslan to call for Islamic unity. He demonstrates how colonial

narratives were successful in manipulating Muslim perceptions, stating, “They have gone on blowing their horn of hopelessness until the propaganda of weakness was gradually absorbed by the ordinary folk” (Arslan, 97). The British sought to redefine Muslim governance on their terms as seen in Ostrorog’s statement that the Ottoman Caliphate was a “sham” while Britain’s proxy ruler was “fact” (Ostrorog, 27), a tactic used to push for abandoning the Ottoman Caliphate. The Khilafat Movement (1919-1924) in India where Indian muslims mobilized to defend the Ottoman Caliphate against British intervention shows how this was not a Muslim thought, but a constructed British manipulation. Arslan exposes colonial perception management designed to convince Muslim’s of their inferiority, particularly through false statistics that downplayed the global Muslim population - a major threat to the West - and misrepresented calculations for projects like the Hijaz railway: “I know how uneasy Europeans are with the rising number of Muslims. Hence, they always minimize their numbers and their importance...apparently malicious intentions” (Arslan, 115). Therefore, rather than passively accepting British intervention he calls for pan-Islamic solidarity, arguing, “the Two Holy Places belong to all Muslims, not to the Arabs alone” (Arslan, 113). He critiques the nationalization and monopolization of sacred islamic sites and their administration, asserting that Saudi Arabia alone could not claim exclusive responsibility, nor afford their management alone. Arslan’s argument reframes the Muslim world as an interconnected force, with cooperation like the joint Egyptian-Saudi infrastructure investments, demonstrating the potential for revival through unity and self-determination.

Overall, colonial powers sustained their dominance over the Islamic world, and secured their power in global politics, not only through military and political control but through psychological subjugation, historical revisionism, and the calculated dismantling of Islamic governance. Ostrorog’s text exemplifies how British officials positioned themselves as both arbiters and architects of Pan-Islamic affairs, using strategic paternalism to justify imperialism while systematically weakening Muslim sovereignty. Arslan, in contrast, exposes how this interference eroded Muslim self-confidence under the guise of Western-constructed narratives of Islamic weakness. Together, these texts reveal how colonial forces manufactured dependency, fostering the illusion that Muslim progress was impossible without

Western oversight, ultimately containing Islamic governance to serve imperial interests. The struggle over Pan-Islamism and the Caliphate reflects a broader reality: colonial influence outlived its direct rule and embedded itself in governance, economy, and identity long after its departure.

Works Cited

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